

In-vitro Evaluation of Aqueous Leaf Extract of *Aloe vera* L. Against Seedling Growth of Green Gram (*Vigna radiata* L.)

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ABSTRACT

In present investigation the aqueous leaf extract of *Aloe vera* L. was prepared at 1 to 5 % concentration using fresh leaves of *Aloe vera* L. These concentrations were used against seedling growth of green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.). The results were recorded that, out of five concentrations, length of root, shoot fresh and dry weight were prohibited up to 3 % concentration. At % concentration 4 and 5 inhibition were recorded. This is may be due to optimum level of nutrients, enzymes and phytochemicals present in leaf extract of *Aloe vera* L.

Keywords: *Aloe vera* L., *Vigna radiata* L. root, shoot, fresh, dry weight

INTRODUCTION

In agriculture challenges related to crop production is increasing day by day due to climate change, erosion, pollution and non-sustainable farming practices. The imbalanced application of chemical fertilizers, pesticides increase the crop production problems as cause in underground water pollution imbalance of soil nutrients and health issue of whole biosphere. With this view the development of biostimulant has drawn considerable interest in recent year (Bulgari *et al.*, 2019, Nephali *et al.*, 2020, Yakhin 2017). Any substances or microorganisms when applied to crop plant helps to nutrient uptake, reduces a biotic stress, increase in quality crop yield called as plant bio-stimulant. The several plant extracts are good sources of organic bio stimulants. The *Aloe vera* leaf extract is one of them. (Yakhin 2017, Bulgari *et al.*, 2019, Nephali *et al.*, 2020,).

The allelochemicals have been documented to exert either a stimulatory effect (positive allelopathy) or an inhibitory effect (negative allelopathy) on target organisms (Bhowmik and Inderjit, 2003; Rice, 1984). These Allelopathic components affect the % seed germination and plant growth. The Allelochemicals with a prohibitory effect acts as bio stimulators and bio-fertilizers to improve crop health development and overall yield (Lin *et al.*, 2004; Popa *et al.*, 2008; Bhadha *et al.*, 2014). The heterogeneous compounds present in *Aloe vera* L. pulp may contribute to the diverse

pharmacological and therapeutic activities that have been observed for *Aloe vera* L. gel products. This plant has been traditionally utilized in traditional system of medicine for the treatment of fever, skin diseases, diabetes, hypertension and helminthiasis. The medicinal importance of, this review *Aloe vera* L. as aimed at compiling all currently available botanical, phytochemicals, pharmacological, and toxicological and ethno- medical information on *Aloe vera* L. mechanisms of action.

The genus *Aloe* belongs to the family Alliaceae, and includes more than 400 species. The *Aloe vera* (L.) is most famous for folk medicine Burm. f. or *Aloe arborescence* Miller. *Aloe vera* L. originated in the warm, dry climates of Africa, the plant is readily adaptable and grows worldwide (Steenkamp & Stewart, 2007). The cactus is characterized by the possibility to store large volumes of water in its tissue. *Aloe* plants have green fleshy leaves covered by a thick cuticle or rind, under which is a thin vascular layer covering an inner clear pulp. The leaves are 30-50 cm in length and 10 cm in width at the base, pea-green in color and with bright yellow tubular flowers 25-35 cm in length. The main feature of the *Aloe vera* L. plant is its highwater content, ranging from 99% to 99.5 %, while the remaining 0.5–1.0% solid material is reported to contain over 200 different potentially active compounds, including vitamins, minerals, enzymes, simple and complex polysaccharides, phenolic compounds, and organic acids (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2010).

Green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.) is leguminous pulse crop belongs to family fabaceae, mainly grown in Maharashtra, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh. It is rich source of protein and fibers. *Aloe vera* gel is rich in minerals like calcium, iron, potassium, magnesium, phosphorous, and zinc. Enzymes like catalyze, amylase, oxidase, lipase, and superoxide dismutase. Amino acids like algenine, glycine, and proline. Vitamins like, B-complex, C, B bita carotene, alfatokoferrol, and phytohormone like gibberellins, indoacetic acid, and abscisic acid were recorded (Abbas *et al.*, 2016, El sheriff *et al.* 2017, 2020., Godlewaska *et al.*, 2020).

With this view of, presence of such source of nutrients in *Aloe vera* L. leaf the present study was designed to examine in-vitro influences of aqueous extract of *Aloe vera* L. against green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.) as bio-stimulant.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Collection of plant material: The leaves of *Aloe vera* L. was collected in dry polythene bag and brought to the laboratory for further study. The test plant Green Gram (*Vigna radiata* L.) was used. The seeds with uniform size, color and weight were selected. These seeds then dipped in water; those seeds settled at bottom were used for the experimental purpose.

Preparation of Aloe vera leaf extract: *Aloe vera* leaves (longer than 40 cm) were washed and sliced into 2 equal parts in a longitudinal section. Leaf gel was scraped off with the help of a knife. The mixture was homogenized with the help of mixture and grinder for 2 min and concentrations of 1% to 5% with distilled water were prepared for further investigation and Control with distilled water.

Determination of Root no. and Root length: The leaf extract was applied at the following rates of Concentrations, 1% to 5% and Distilled Water only as Control, 5 seeds of *Vigna radiata* L. were placed in each plate for germination. Triplicate set of each treatment was investigated at 5th day of germination, percent germination and seedling growth in (cm) was recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To check green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.) treated with different concentrations of *Aloe vera* L. (for 5 days at room temperature) are shown in Table-1. Our results showed that all tested concentrations of *Aloe vera* L. gel extracts, In the control, root length 3.2 cm. and shoot length is 7.2 however, after application of 1% and 2% gel extract concentration the Root length was estimated to be respectively 4.3 cm and 7.2 cm and shoot length 8.4 and 9.5. Root length with a green gram treated with 3% *A. vera* gel extract show maximum Root length 8.2 cm and shoot length 10.2, and 4% and 5 % concentration gradually decrease shoot length and root length (Table 1). In a similar way, our results supported these data and showed that shoot and root growth rate decreased in parallel to the increasing concentrations of gel extracts except 3 % of *Aloe vera* L. leaf extract. The results of this study indicate that the Allelopathic effect of *Aloe vera* gel extracts depend on their concentration, with even the low doses demonstrating a considerable rate of stimulating and inhibition in shoot and root growth rate.

Table 1: Effect of *Aloe vera* L. Leaf Extract on Seedling Growth of Green Gram (*Vigna radiata* L.)

Concentration of Leaf extract of <i>Aloe vera</i> L. (%)	Average Shoot Growth (Cm)	Average Root Growth (Cm)	Average Seedling Growth (Cm)	Fresh weight (gm)	Dry weight (gm)
Control	7.2	3.2	10.4	3.11	1.14
1%	8.4	4.3	12.7	3.58	1.28
2%	9.5	7.2	16.7	4.23	2.10
3%	10.2	8.2	18.4	4.59	2.23
4%	7.2	6.1	13.3	4.41	1.69
5%	6.2	4.2	10.4	3.96	1.39

Graph 1: Effect of *Aloe vera* L. Leaf Extract on Seedling Growth of Green Gram (*Vigna radiata* L.)

Graph2: Effect of *Aloe vera* L. leaf extract on Fresh weight and Dry Weight of green gram (*Vigna radiata* L.)

Photo plate: - Effect of *Aloe vera* L. Leaf Extract on Seedling Growth of Green Gram (*Vigna radiata* L.)

Table 2: Analysis of Chemical Parameters of *Aloe vera* L. Leaf Extracts

Conc. Of <i>Aloe vera</i> leaf extract	pH	EC	Sodium	Potassium	Carbonate
1%	7.72	0.19	0.43	0.51	00
2%	7.74	0.20	0.82	1.28	00
3%	7.74	0.21	0.86	1.28	00
4%	7.76	0.22	0.86	1.28	00
5%	7.78	0.25	0.88	1.30	00

CONCLUSION

It is calculated that, *Aloe vera* L. leaf extract is luxuriant growth of shoot and root length by 3% concentration, in the root and shoot as compared to control. It can be concluded that the untreated reduced the crop growth. However, the stimulation of growth yield was observed at 5 % concentration. 3 % concentration of *Aloe vera* L. extract recorded maximum root, shoot length fresh and dry weight of (green gram) *Vigna radiata* L.

Aloe vera L. leaf extracts exerted the above result concentration correlated as the concentration increase, increase in shoot, root length fresh and dry weight.

The green gram grower farmers can improve seed germination using 3% *Aloe vera* L. leaf extracts without harm to soil, beneficial micro flora as well as ecosystem. It may also help to enhance physical and chemical properties of soil.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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